

Shilluk

Data source: eHRAF

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Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: African Religions, Religious Group

This entry focuses on the Shilluk around the time of 1910. At the time this entry focuses on, the Shilluk lived along the banks of the White Nile, in what is now South Sudan. Groups of several households formed hamlets, which were each led by a chief. The chiefs were directly responsible to the king, who served as head of both political and religious affairs. Shilluk kings are said to possess the spirit Nyakang, the founder of the Shilluk and first king. Three major components of Shilluk religious beliefs are Juok (the supreme high god, an otiose creator deity), Nyakang and his incarnation through kings, and ancestor worship. Throughout Shilluk territory are 10 cenotaphs "tombs" of Nyakang, which are regarded as the homes of Nyakang. Similar shrines to deceased kings are also present. The attendants and priests of the royal grave shrines and cenotaph shrines of Nyakang are referred to as the bareth. The bareth were responsible for maintaining the shrine, receiving sacrifices, and officiating in ceremonies. Two classes of medicine men are present, including the ajuago (the good medicine man, who works for the good of the community and cures the sick) and the jalyat (the evil medicine man, who practices black magic). Because religion permeates almost all aspects of life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with society itself.

Date Range: 1895 CE - 1925 CE

Region: Shilluk lands, ca. 1910

Region tags: Africa, Eastern Africa, South Sudan

Shilluk lands, ca. 1910

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. (2004). Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research.
- Source 2: Murdock, G.P. (1967). Ethnographic Atlas. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Source 3: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 3. Ethnology, 11(3), 254-295.
- Source 1: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. Ethnology, 11(4), 436-464.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fj23-002>
- Source 1 Description: Seligman, C. G. (Charles G., & Seligman, B. Z. (1932). Pagan tribes of the Nilotic Sudan. George Routledge and Sons Ltd.
- Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fj23-000>
- Source 2 Description: Burton, J. W. (2010). Culture Summary: Shilluk. Human Relations Area Files.
- Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fj23-028>
- Source 3 Description: Oyler, D. S. (1918). Nikawng's place in the Shilluk religion. Sudan Notes and Records, Vol. 1, 283-292.
- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fj23-013>
- Source 1 Description: Oyler, D. S. (1920). The Shilluk's belief in the good medicine men. Sudan Notes and Records, Vol. 3, 110-116.
- Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fj23-031>
- Source 2 Description: Westermann, D. (1912). Introduction. In The Shilluk people, their language and folklore (pp. XIX – LXIV). The Board of Foreign Missions of the United Presbyterian Church of North America.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "Islam does up to now not find much sympathy with the Shilluks. They prefer their own religion to that of foreigners. Only a few people who have for a longer time lived in close touch with Mohammedans, chiefly those who have served as soldiers, adopt the religion of Mohammed..." (Westermann, 1912:XLV). Westermann also describes Christian missions in Sudan (see 1912, pp.LX-LXIII).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (resolved rating) coded the Shilluk as 11 (original code 3.5) which is between 9 (internal warfare seems to occur once every 3-10 years; original code 2) and 13 (internal warfare seems to occur every year, but usually only during a particular season; original code 4). Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (resolved rating) coded the Shilluk as 9 (original code 3) which indicates "external warfare seems to occur at least once every two years (original code 3)." Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the Shilluk would actively proselytize and recruit new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: "The Shilluk king is absolute head—temporal and spiritual—of a state whose territory is divided into a number of provinces, each administered by a chief directly responsible to the sovereign and acting as his proxy" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:39).

Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

Notes: "The Shilluk king is absolute head—temporal and spiritual—of a state whose territory is divided into a number of provinces, each administered by a chief directly responsible to the sovereign and acting as his proxy" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:39).

Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– I don't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of a conception of apostasy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 100000

Notes: "...at the present time it is likely that the Shilluk number some 100,000" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:37).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The attendants and priests of the royal grave shrines and the cenotaph shrines of Nyakang are known as bareth (lit. 'king's wife'). This term includes certain old men, who appear to have a hereditary connection with the shrine (but on this matter we are unable to be precise), ex-wives of kings, who having borne a reasonable number of children or attained menopause are sent to take charge of shrines, and men and women of advanced years who are liable to more or less epileptiform attacks, held to indicate possession by Nyakang or a dead king. The bareth keep the shrine clean, receive the sacrifices, and officiate in the ceremonies..." (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:77). "The 'medicine-men' of

the Shilluk are of two kinds, the ajuago—literally 'the man of Juok' (God)—the good medicine-man, who generally speaking works for the good of the community (though from the administrative standpoint his acts may be reprehensible), including the cure of the sick, and the evil medicineman, the jalyat—literally 'the man of herbs'—dealing essentially in black magic, or the satisfaction of private rather than public ends" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:99).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:
– I don't know

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:
– Yes

Notes: "The power of the ajuago is due to the immanence of the spirits of the early Shilluk kings. The guardians of the shrine of Nyakang might or might not be ajuago; they do not become ajuago because of their connection with the shrine, nor does their being ajuago alter their official position. According to our most reliable informant, only the spirits of Nyakang, Dag, and Boc (the first, third, and seventh of the Shilluk kings) become immanent in men to make them ajuago" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:100).

↳ Powers are inherited:
– Yes

Notes: "The occult power may also descend on the descendants of a son or a daughter of a medicine man, who did not inherit that power, and the fact that the power of working charms comes to a person whose father was not a witch doctor may be explained as a proof of the return of the power of some forgotten ancestor" (Oyler, 1920:110).

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:
– Yes

Notes: "The people are not agreed as to the source whence the medicine man receives his power. Some maintain that the power comes from God, and others, that it is a heritage from the man's ancestors" (Oyler, 1920:110).

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
– I don't know

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
– Yes

Notes: "However after a man has once established his reputation failure does not have such a serious effect on his practice" (Oyler, 1920:111)

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:
– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates charges would be incurred as a result of fallibility.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates charges would be incurred as a result of fallibility.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates charges would be incurred as a result of fallibility.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– I don't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of scripture.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to Murdock and Wilson (1972) Column 6, Large or Impressive Structures, indicates "there are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings."

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: "There are ten cenotaph 'tombs' of Nyakang (kengo Nyakang) in the Shilluk country, the most important being at Akurwa and Fenikang. Each shrine consists of a group of two or more huts—of the same circular form but rather larger than dwelling huts—together with a small more or less circular enclosure, called ludi, neatly fenced with millet stalks" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:77).

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: "Like the cenotaph shrines of Nyakang the royal grave shrines are called kengo, as opposed to the graves of commoners for which the word is roro. Though smaller, they resemble the shrines of Nyakang in appearance...The guardians or priests (bareth) of these shrines are of the same class as those of the kengo Nyakang...Just as no one except the bareth Nyakang is allowed to enter the shrines of Nyakang, so no stranger may enter the royal grave shrines" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:89).

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Cenotaphs

Notes: "The spirit of Nyakang is regarded as closely associated with certain shrines, which are in fact cenotaphs, for though spoken of as his tombs it is well known that he is not buried in any of them" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:77).

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: "We may here refer to the special regard paid to trees growing near the shrines of dead kings, which we consider yet another aspect of the cult of Nyakang...When a tree has grown, or is believed to have grown, near a shrine shortly after its erection, i.e. within a few months or years of the burial of a "divine king", it is thought that the tree has sprung from one of the logs used in making the grave, and in such cases the relation between the tree and the dead king is one that would easily suggest itself" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:87).

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Seligman and Seligman, 1932:87

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "Every living man has both wei and tipo, the former signifying 'breath', 'life', the latter 'shadow', 'image', as in water or mirror. We have already referred to the cen of one dying in anger and malevolence (p. 97), and there is a word aneko, meaning ghost, i.e. the spirit of one dead" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:103).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "There is an expression pan Juok, 'the country of Juok'. We formed the opinion that though this implied no local habitation it was vaguely associated with the dead; Hofmayr [missionary and author of other work describing the Shilluk] is more definite, regarding pan Juok as the place of Nyakang and the ancestors, to be reached after many months journeying in the bush" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:75).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: See the questions below for more information regarding the spatial location of the afterlife.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

Notes: Seligman and Seligman, 1932:75

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

Notes: Seligman and Seligman, 1932:75

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

Notes: "There is an expression pan Juok, 'the country of Juok'. We formed the opinion that though this implied no local habitation it was vaguely associated with the dead; Hofmayr [missionary and author of other work describing the Shilluk] is more definite, regarding pan Juok as the place of Nyakang and the ancestors, to be reached after many months journeying in the bush" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:75).

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: "Each Shilluk king incarnates the spirit of Nyakang [culture hero and first king of Shilluk; described in section on Supernatural Beings, Mixed Human-Divine]" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:77).

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: "Each Shilluk king incarnates the spirit of Nyakang [culture hero and first king of Shilluk; described in section on Supernatural Beings, Mixed Human-Divine]" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:77).

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is only described as occurring in human form. Specifically, the spirit of Nyakang is reincarnated in kings. (see Seligman and Seligman, 1932:77).

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is only described as occurring in human form. Specifically, the spirit of Nyakang is reincarnated in kings. (see Seligman and Seligman, 1932:77).

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– Yes

Notes: "Each Shilluk king incarnates the spirit of Nyakang [culture hero and first king of Shilluk; described in section on Supernatural Beings, Mixed Human-Divine]" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:77).

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– No

Notes: Reincarnation is only described as occurring in human form. Specifically, the spirit of Nyakang is reincarnated in kings. (see Seligman and Seligman, 1932:77).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "A skin is placed in the grave and the body laid upon it wrapped in a white cloth (this is a recent introduction) and covered with another skin. The position of the hands is uncertain; we were told that they were laid between the knees, and also that they were placed in front of the face" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:103).

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of cremation. Only internment is described.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of mummification. Only internment is described.

↳ **Interment:**

– Yes

Notes: "A skin is placed in the grave and the body laid upon it wrapped in a white cloth (this is a recent introduction) and covered with another skin. The position of the hands is uncertain; we were told that they were laid between the knees, and also that they were placed in front of the face" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:103).

↳ **Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):**

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified.

↳ **Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):**

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified.

↳ **Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):**

– I don't know

Notes: Not specified.

↳ **Cannibalism:**

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of cannibalism. Only internment is described.

↳ **Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):**

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates corpses were exposed to the elements. Only internment is described.

↳ **Feeding to animals:**

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates corpses were fed to animals. Only internment is described.

↳ **Secondary burial:**

– I don't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: "When a man dies two fowls are killed, one being placed at the head of the deceased. An ox and a goat are also sacrificed" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:103). The authors note that this description applies to wealthy and important men, elaborating "...we believe that for a poor man cattle are not always killed" (ibid).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Human sacrifices present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of human sacrifice.

Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: "When a man dies two fowls are killed, one being placed at the head of the deceased. An ox and a goat are also sacrificed" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:103). The authors note that this description applies to wealthy and important men, elaborating "...we believe that for a poor man cattle are not always killed" (ibid).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Notes: "Nothing is buried with the corpse, but later a hole is made near and objects placed in it" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:103).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: For a full description of funeral practices see Seligman and Seligman (1932, pp. 103-104).

As cenotaphs:

– I don't know

In cemetery:

– I don't know

Notes: "Burial is at full length, a few paces from the door of the house in which the deceased lived" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:103).

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– I don't know

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: "Burial is at full length, a few paces from the door of the house in which the deceased lived" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:103).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "Shilluk religious concepts are drawn into relief by an emphasis on the creator-god or divinity known as Juok (a common Nilotic term for a spiritual power), the veneration of Nyakang through the persons who become kings, and the recognition of the ways in which the spirits of the deceased can affect those who survive them" (Burton, 2010).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: "Juok is formless and invisible, and, like the air, is everywhere at once. He is far above Nyakang (in whose cult the Shilluk religion centres) and men alike; nevertheless it is principally through Nyakang that men approach him, performing the sacrifices to Nyakang which cause him to move Juok to send rain" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:74). "Juok, vaguely associated with the firmament, is recognized as the creator, though now showing but little interest in his creatures" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:75).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: "Juok, vaguely associated with the firmament, is recognized as the creator, though now showing but little interest in his creatures" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:75).

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– Yes

Notes: "Summing up, we may say that Juok is the Creator, perhaps vaguely associated with the firmament, but certainly having a chthonic aspect" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:75).

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates Juok is fused with the monarch (see Seligman and Seligman, 1932:75).

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Many of the people say that if a man refuses to consult the medicine men, God will be angry with that person, and leave him to get along without help, which means that he will be cut off from all supernatural aid" (Oyler, 1920:112).

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Oyler, 1920:112

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Juok is formless and invisible, and, like the air, is everywhere at once. He is far above Nyakang (in whose cult the Shilluk religion centres) and men alike; nevertheless it is principally through Nyakang that men approach him, performing the sacrifices to Nyakang which cause him to move Juok to send rain" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:74).

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– No

Notes: Because Juok is viewed as otiose, it does not appear Juok communicates with the living (see Seligman and Seligman, 1932:75).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The third element in the Shilluk religion is the cult of ancestors (other than those of the royal family)" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:96).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: The spirits of deceased kings are described as able to appear to the living through dreams (see Seligman and Seligman, 1932:89).

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Many of the medicine men have physical defects, and their children are usually sickly, and many of them are deformed. The natives say that this is caused by the fact that the shades of their victims bring a curse on the medicine man, and also on his family" (Oyler, 1920:111).

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "Many of the medicine men have physical defects, and their children are usually sickly, and many of them are deformed. The natives say that this is caused by the fact that the shades of their victims bring a curse on the medicine man, and also on his family" (Oyler, 1920:111).

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "...the spirit persists in or around the grave and may harm its living relatives, e.g. the death of a missionary's wife shortly after that of her husband was attributed to the ghost of the latter" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:96).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: "The servants of the king claim the power to converse with the dead" (Oyler, 1918:290).

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: "The spirit of the king then takes powerful possession of the medium, and she speaks in a peculiar voice" (Oyler, 1918:290).

↳ Only through specialists:

– Yes

Notes: "The servants of the king claim the power to converse with the dead" (Oyler, 1918:290).

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: "The servants of the king claim the power to converse with the dead" (Oyler, 1918:290).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "...the Shilluk believes in various more or less anthropomorphic but non-human beings dwelling in bush and river, the most important of these being the river-people, with whom are associated herds of supernatural river-cattle" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:74). Although these supernatural beings are mentioned, they are not described in extensive ethnographic detail.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "...the majority of Shilluk think of Nyakang as a divine or semi-divine being, human in form and physical qualities, though, unlike his recent successors, he did not die but disappeared in a great storm of wind during a festival held at Akurwa..." (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:76).

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "...we [authors] believe that to many of his worshippers, including some at least of his priests, Nyakang is essentially a spiritual being, who manifests himself to humanity by way of incarnation or sometimes (as in dreams) as a bright light" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:76).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: "They [the Shilluk] maintain that Nikawng still lives. He is even now watching over the Shilluks..." (Oyler, 1918:285). "The spirit of Nyakang is regarded as being present, at any rate at certain times, in his wooden effigy kept at Akurwa" (Seligman

and Seligman, 1932:77).

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
– Yes

Notes: Nyakang is described as able to appear to the living through dreams (see Seligman and Seligman, 1932:89).

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

Notes: Nyakang is described as able to appear to the living through dreams (see Seligman and Seligman, 1932:89).

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

Notes: Nyakang is not described as communicating exclusively through the monarch (see Seligman and Seligman, 1932:89).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

Notes: "Shilluk religious concepts are drawn into relief by an emphasis on the creator-god or divinity known as Juok (a common Nilotic term for a spiritual power), the veneration of Nyikang through the persons who become kings, and the recognition of the ways in which the spirits of the deceased can affect those who survive them" (Burton, 2010).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Although indirect supernatural punishment, there is some evidence for a belief in supernatural punishment. Although this topic is not discussed in extensive ethnographic detail, see questions below for available information. "Many of the medicine men have physical defects, and their children are usually sickly, and many of them are deformed. The natives say that this is caused by the fact that the

shades of their victims bring a curse on the medicine man, and also on his family" (Oyler, 1920:111). "Many of the people say that if a man refuses to consult the medicine men, God will be angry with that person, and leave him to get along without help, which means that he will be cut off from all supernatural aid" (Oyler, 1920:112).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: The agent of supernatural punishment is described as both the high god (Juok) and the spirits of deceased humans (see Oyler, 1920:111-112).

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: The agent of supernatural punishment is described as both the high god (Juok) and the spirits of deceased humans (see Oyler, 1920:111-112).

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The agent of supernatural punishment is described as both the high god (Juok) and the spirits of deceased humans (see Oyler, 1920:111-112).

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for available information regarding reasons for supernatural punishment.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– I don't know

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– I don't know

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– I don't know

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates supernatural punishment would occur randomly.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: "Many of the people say that if a man refuses to consult the medicine men, God will be angry with that person, and leave him to get along without help, which means that he will be cut off from all supernatural aid" (Oyler, 1920:112). "Many of the medicine men have physical defects, and their children are usually sickly, and many of them are deformed. The natives say that this is caused by the fact that the shades of their victims bring a curse on the medicine man, and also on his family" (Oyler, 1920:111).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of supernatural punishment meted out in the afterlife.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below.

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: "Many of the medicine men have physical defects, and their children are usually sickly, and many of them are deformed. The natives say that this is caused by the fact that the shades of their victims bring a curse on the medicine man, and also on his family" (Oyler, 1920:111)

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: "Many of the medicine men have physical defects, and their children are usually sickly, and many of them are deformed. The natives say that this is caused by the fact that the shades of their victims bring a curse on the medicine man, and also on his family" (Oyler, 1920:111)

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: "Many of the people say that if a man refuses to consult the medicine men, God will be angry with that person, and leave him to get along without help, which means that he will be cut off from all supernatural aid" (Oyler, 1920:112).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of an eschatology.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required fasting

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: "There are numerous observances connected with animals, including some which might be called taboos, but we did not ourselves discover any definite evidence of totemism, though as already stated clan exogamy prevails" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:41).

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the requirement of painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: "Human sacrifice was always rare among the Shilluk, but it undoubtedly occurred" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:98).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: "Human sacrifice was always rare among the Shilluk, but it undoubtedly occurred" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:98).

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: "Human sacrifice was always rare among the Shilluk, but it undoubtedly occurred" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:98).

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required physical risk-taking.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: "The worship of Nyakang at Fenikang and his other shrines consists of a solemn ritual of sacrifice and prayer. We [authors] know of the following occasions for ceremonial worship; no doubt there are others of which we did not hear, and we do not doubt that sacrifice would be made in any threat of national danger or disaster. We give in brief outline accounts of the two most important annual ceremonies:— 1. The rain-making ceremony held before the rains at the beginning of the

month labor, at the new moon (the Shilluk calendar is lunar). 2. The harvest festival held when the millet is cut, i.e. about the end of the rains" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:80).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: According to Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1967) Column 32: Jurisdictional Hierarchy, the Shilluk had one level of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a petty chiefdom. "The Shilluk king is absolute head—temporal and spiritual—of a state whose territory is divided into a number of provinces, each administered by a chief directly responsible to the sovereign and acting as his proxy" (Seligman and Seligman, 1932:39).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of formal education.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: Tuden and Marshall (1972) column 10, Police (note, equivalent to SCCS variable 90, Police) indicates that "police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social

control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery."

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Shilluk relied mainly on extensive or shifting agriculture, with animal husbandry to supplement the diet. Gathering, hunting, and fishing also supplemented the diet. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Shilluk relied mainly on extensive or shifting agriculture, with animal husbandry to supplement the diet. Gathering, hunting, and fishing also supplemented the diet. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.